

© Open Cities AI Challenge

Quezon City, Philippines

Microsoft

OpenStreetMap

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Overture

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Microsoft

Google

Overture

Google
Open Buildings
Temporal 2.5D

**Google
Open Buildings
Temporal 2.5D**

**Google
Open Buildings
Temporal 2.5D**

**Climate &
Disaster Risk
Intelligence**

Exposure

Vulnerability

Hazard

**Changing
Vulnerability**

**Earthquake
Hazard**

**Changing
Exposure**

UNIVERSITY OF
CAMBRIDGE

Modernizing Quezon City's Building Risk Data with AI and Earth Observation

Joshua Dimasaka
University of Cambridge
joshuadimasaka.com
jtd33@cam.ac.uk

Fouad Bendimerad
Earthquakes and Megacities Initiative

Renan Ma. Tanhueco
Earthquakes and Megacities Initiative
De La Salle University

Christian Geiß
German Aerospace Center
University of Bonn

Emily So
University of Cambridge

Quezon City, Philippines

A satellite map of a coastal region, likely in the Philippines, showing a city and surrounding areas. A white outline highlights a specific region within the city. The map is oriented vertically, with the coastline on the left and the inland area on the right. The text is overlaid on the left side of the map.

Regional Risk

Six Districts
142 Barangays

Mw-7.2
West Valley Fault

Various Regional Earthquake Risk Assessment Studies for the Greater Metro Manila Area, Philippines

Various Regional Earthquake Risk Assessment Studies for the Greater Metro Manila Area, Philippines

OFFICIAL

MMEIRS and Risk Analysis Project Reports

2004

Earthquake Impact Reduction Study for Metro Manila (MMEIRS)

Executive Summary

Earthquake Impact Reduction Study for Metro Manila (MMEIRS)

(Metro Manila)
34k deaths
114k injured

2014

Enhancing Risk Analysis Capacities for Flood, Tropical Cyclone Severe Wind and Earthquake for Greater Metro Manila Area (GMMMA-Risk Analysis Project)

Summary Report

Risk Analysis Project SUMMARY REPORT

(Greater Metro Manila Area)
37k deaths
605k injured

Enhancing Risk Analysis Capacities for Flood, Tropical Cyclone Severe Wind and Earthquake for Greater Metro Manila Area (GMMMA-Risk Analysis Project)

Earthquake Risk Analysis

Component 5 – Earthquake Risk Analysis

2022

(Quezon City)
12.5k deaths
147k injured

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Stanford

2022

From Deterministic
to Probabilistic
Earthquake Hazard

Various Regional Earthquake Risk Assessment Studies for the Greater Metro Manila Area, Philippines

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Earthquake Risk Analysis

Component 5 – Earthquake Risk Analysis

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(Quezon City)
12.5k deaths
147k injured

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

2022

From Deterministic to Probabilistic Earthquake Hazard

2025

Spatiotemporal Risk via Artificial Intelligence and Earth Observation

Hazard

Earthquake

Mw-7.2 West Valley Fault

Dynamic Exposure

2016

2017

2018

2019

2020

2021

Dynamic Exposure

Physical Vulnerability

Physical Vulnerability Composition

100%

=

Area-based Approach

“Weakly Supervised” + “Spatiotemporal” + “Compositional Data Analysis” problem:

“Deep” Bayesian Update Framework

Previous Studies on Dynamic Exposure & Vulnerability Modelling

Rule-based Approach
(Schorlemmer et al., 2020)

GFZ

<https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/globaldynamicexposure>

[Global Dynamic Exposure · GitLab](#)

a big data exposure model for the world. website:

<https://global.dynamicexposure.org/>. 0. 4. 0. Created Jul 10, 2020....

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◆ Global Dynamic Exposure

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**Cellular Automata
with Markov chains**
(Lallemant, 2015;
Lallemant et al., 2017)

Urban Expansion

Transition Matrix —
$$\begin{pmatrix} p_{0,0} & p_{0,1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & p_{1,1} & p_{1,2} & p_{1,3} \\ 0 & 0 & p_{2,2} & p_{2,3} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & p_{3,3} \end{pmatrix}$$
 — Urban Densification

Previous Studies on Dynamic Exposure & Vulnerability Modelling

Rule-based Approach
(Schorlemmer et al., 2020)

Cellular Automata
with Markov chains

**Multi-agent Systems +
Geographic Regression**
(Calderon and Silva, 2022)

Global Dynamic Exposure

$$p_{tr} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(b_0 + b_1 w_1 + b_2 w_2 + \dots + b_n w_n)}}$$

Previous Studies on Dynamic Exposure & Vulnerability Modelling

Rule-based Approach
(Schorlemmer et al., 2020)

Cellular Automata with Markov chains
(Lallemant, 2015; Lallemant et al., 2017)

Multi-agent Systems + Geographic Regression
(Calderon and Silva, 2022)

Analytical Bayesian Probabilistic Modeling
(Porter et al., 2014; Pittore et al., 2020)

Global Dynamic Exposure

GFZ
<https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/globaldynamicexposure>
Global Dynamic Exposure - GitLab
 a big data exposure model for the world. website: <https://global.dynamicexposure.org/>. 0. 4. 0. Created Jul 10, 2020...

$$P_{tr} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(b_0 + b_1 w_1 + b_2 w_2 + \dots + b_n w_n)}}$$

$$p(\mathbf{n}|\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \text{Mul}(\mathbf{n}|\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{N!}{n_1! \dots n_k!} \theta_1^{n_1} \dots \theta_k^{n_k}$$

GraphVSSM:
Graph
Variational
State-
Space
Model

Graph VSSM

At time t ,
the state-space model
(SSM) consists of:

V: Vulnerability Composition

E: Exposure Presence

X: Satellite Imagery (auxiliary)

GraphVSSM

OE: Observation Exposure

TE: Transition Exposure

OV: Observation Vulnerability

TV: Transition Vulnerability

Graph_VSSM

Variational learning (deep probabilistic)

OE

Building Height $\sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_\theta(\mathbf{X}), \Sigma_\theta(\mathbf{X}))$

TE

Building Presence $\sim \text{Bern}(p_\theta(\mathbf{X}))$

OV

Vulnerability Composition $\sim \text{Mult}(p_\theta^1(\mathbf{X}), \dots, p_\theta^K(\mathbf{X}))$

TV

GraphVSSM

10-meter resolution

Unstructured Data of Built Environment

Building Height: 6m

Red of RGB: 0.0997

Green of RGB: 0.1218

Blue of RGB: 0.1378

Near-Infrared: 0.2078

Short-Wave Infrared 1: 0.1741

Dataset

Dataset

Red of RGB

Green of RGB

Blue of RGB

Near-Infrared

Short-Wave Infrared 1

Dataset

	Bare Area Extraction Index (BAEI)				
	Urbanization Index (UI)				
	Norm. Urban Areas Composite Index (NUACI)				
	Norm. Diff. Water Index (NDWI)				

Dataset

	Bare Area Extraction Index (BAEI)				
	Urbanization Index (UI)				
	Norm. Urban Areas Composite Index (NUACI)				
	Proximity to Main Road Networks				

Dataset

	Bare Area Extraction Index (BAEI)				
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	Proximity to Main Road Networks				

 Building Presence as a 'Bernoulli' Variable

 Building Height as a 'LogNormal' Variable

Dataset

	Bare Area Extraction Index (BAEI)				
	Urbanization Index (UI)				
	Norm. Urban Areas Composite Index (NUACI)				
	Proximity to Main Road Networks				

 Building Presence as a 'Bernoulli' Variable

 Building Height as a 'LogNormal' Variable

 Physical Vulnerability Composition as a 'MultiNomial' Variable

Dataset

Feature & Label (Prior)

Feature & Label (Prior)

Feature & Label (Prior)

Graphical Structure

Graph Deep Learning

Barangay Blue Ridge B

Table 70. Earthquake Hotspot Barangays as Established by the 3-tier Barangay Vulnerability Index (BVI).

Earthquake Hotspot Barangays				
Tier	Rank	Barangay	BVI	District
Tier 1 Very High Vulnerability	1	Blue Ridge B	100	3
	2	Batasan Hills	92	2
	3	Ugong Norte	90	3
	4	Bagong Silangan	89	2
	5	Escopa 4	88	3
	6	Blue Ridge A	88	3

Dynamic Exposure

Building Presence $\sim \text{Bern}(p_\theta(\mathbf{X}))$

Dynamic Exposure

Building Height $\sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_{\theta}(\mathbf{X}), \Sigma_{\theta}(\mathbf{X}))$

Dynamic Vulnerability

$$\text{Composition} \sim \text{Mult}(\mathbf{p}_\theta^1(\mathbf{X}), \dots, \mathbf{p}_\theta^K(\mathbf{X}))$$

Area-based Approach

Dynamic Regional Earthquake Risk

Beyond 2030: UN Sendai Framework

- **AI is not just ChatGPT.** AI, particularly probabilistic deep learning and other emerging frameworks, offers a new approach to problems in geoscience and regional risk assessment, when combined with new forms of EO data.

Beyond 2030: UN Sendai Framework

- AI is not just ChatGPT. AI, particularly probabilistic deep learning and other emerging frameworks, offers a new approach to problems in geoscience and regional risk assessment, when combined with new forms of EO data.
- Tracking spatiotemporal changes in exposure and vulnerability can give local governments comprehensive data-driven insights for an agile, proactive, and effective disaster risk reduction.

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Joshua Dimasaka

joshuadimasaka.com

jtd33@cam.ac.uk

The 40th Annual AAAI
Conference on Artificial
Intelligence

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